

Primer on Open Science Outreach

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Summary

Our work investigated the outreach environment surrounding Open Science in different international settings. We identified barriers for promotion of Open Science and possible mitigations for these. An initial list of available resources related to outreach in Open Science was also compiled. We additionally conducted a pilot survey on the outreach environment of Open Science, finding that our predicted barriers may be a reality to responders. Finally, we reflected on our experience of providing outreach services to Open Science promoters participating in the 2025 Open Science Retreat.

Motivation

There are a lot of Open Science initiatives on various levels such as policy, services, infrastructures. It appears that many initiatives struggle to reach their target audiences, particularly as changing research culture is a slow process and initiatives are often relatively short-term projects.

Oftentimes, it appears that these initiatives predominantly "preach to the choir" by targeting other Open Science advocates or early adopters, but do we even reach the "choir"? What about disciplinary silos as today's data-driven research becomes more inter- or even transdisciplinary? There also seems to be a tension between top-down and bottom-up approaches having an impact on the awareness and success of such Open Science initiatives.

It is therefore important to know more about your target audience in order to tailor promotion and outreach activities for greater impact.

In this primer, we try to identify barriers to engaging in such promotion and outreach activities, and identify potential solutions for overcoming these barriers.

Identifying Barriers & Obstacles for Effective Outreach for Service Providers

Several studies indicate that many researchers are indeed unaware of Open Science and reproducibility initiatives. For instance, a study focusing on UK Psychology PhD researchers found that while there was a general positive attitude towards Open Science, knowledge and perceptions of Open Science tools varied significantly. Many participants reported mixed supervisory support, highlighting gaps in awareness and understanding of Open Science practices ([Pownall et al., 2023](#)). Similarly, a study on early-career researchers in Human-Computer Interaction found key barriers to adopting Open Science practices, including a lack of clear incentives and limited training, which suggests that awareness and engagement are low ([Chakravorti et al., 2024](#)). Moreover, researchers have expressed feelings of alienation from Open Science policies, indicating difficulties in coping with these initiatives and further supporting the notion of a disconnect between policy and practice ([Lilja 2020](#)).

Practices and attitudes are changing slowly. This is manifested in the [value-action gap](#) and change appears to be developing in terms of diffusion of innovation ([Fig. 1](#), e.g., [Dearing & Cox 2018](#)). In that sense, promotion of Open Science initiatives is closely related to the concept of change management (cf., [Manske & Zänkert 2024](#)), which appears to be not widely acknowledged.

Classical approaches to mitigate these factors are training and workshops, such as the Reproducibility for Everyone (R4E) initiative ([Auer et al. 2011](#)) or "The Carpentries" ([Wilson 2016](#)). These are successful endeavours, which are built to educate the never-ending stream of students. Amongst such initiatives are more recent examples, such as teaching reproducible computing ([Petersen et al. 2025](#)).

However, these initiatives, while valuable, often operate as "one-off" interventions. They may not adequately address the long-term, evolving needs of researchers across diverse disciplines and career stages. Furthermore, they frequently fall into the trap of being *supply-driven* – offering training based on what experts *think* service providers need, rather than what researchers *actually* need.

This disconnect highlights a critical flaw in many Open Science outreach strategies: a lack of focus on understanding the end-user. Researchers are not a homogenous group.

A physicist's workflow and challenges will differ drastically from those of a bioinformatics data analyst. Early-career researchers face different pressures than established professors. A one-size-fits-all approach is unlikely to be effective. Without a deep understanding of nuanced needs and barriers, even the most well-intentioned initiatives risk falling flat or, worse, creating further resistance.

Therefore, systematic and repeated user surveys are not merely *helpful* – they are essential. These surveys should go beyond simply measuring awareness. They must probe specific barriers researchers face in adopting Open Science practices *within their specific disciplines*, their current workflows and how tools (e.g. software, storage requirements and other services) can be seamlessly integrated. Less generic options are also possible: focus groups, expert interviews, persona development. We recommend to also address the perceived value of different Open Science practices and incentives, and their training needs.

Failing to conduct such surveys carries significant risks. Resources might be wasted on introducing infrastructure that goes unused. Outreach efforts will be ineffective, and the crucial goal of fostering a culture of Open Science will be delayed. However, the field of Open Science is developing dynamically and evolving constantly. This makes user research and outreach more complex and demanding, particularly considering follow up studies. In severe cases, a lack of engagement can lead to a loss of funding for valuable Open Science services, effectively obliterating any initial outreach activity (e.g. [Karapetrovic et al. 2018](#) for HPC services).

Given the slow pace of change in research practices and culture, demonstrating the value of new Open Science practices by identifying and working with early adopters can be a key activity, as they act as multipliers ([Fig. 1](#)).¹ Such demonstration of value is more easily recognised by peers. To support the adoption of new practices, intellectual ramps have been shown to be helpful in gradually introducing these new practices ([Atkinson et al. 2012](#)). However, this requires dedicated resources that need to be considered in the initial project planning.

In conclusion, successful Open Science implementation demands a user-centred approach. Continuous feedback loops, powered by rigorous user surveys, are vital for ensuring that Open Science initiatives are relevant, accessible, and ultimately, adopted

¹ <https://digitaltonto.com/2024/heres-why-creating-awareness-is-usually-a-waste-of-time/>

by the research community. Investing in understanding the needs of researchers is not an expense – it is a crucial investment in the future of science itself.

Figure 1. Roger's Bell Curve, as adapted by the INOSC (International Network of Open Science & Scholarship Communities, CC-BY NC SA 4.0), to illustrate the timely demand before an Open Science related tool, course set, or other initiative can reach acceptance. After adoption of a tool set or policy by early adopters, reaching and convincing more people will inevitably take more time.

Pilot Survey

As part of our preparation, we mind-mapped potential barriers to engaging in outreach for Open Science initiatives (see Table 1). We conducted an internal pilot survey to investigate whether these barriers reflected the experiences of people involved in open science initiatives. This was conducted in April 2025 as part of the Open Science Retreat in Beatenberg, Switzerland. Survey materials are available in the Appendix.

- Disconnect between researchers, research professionals, and communications staff in universities.
- Overcoming the "noise" (large number of posts), especially on social media and email lists.
- Political, slow-moving, and hierarchical structures.
- Outreach requiring approval from management.
- Competition between initiatives (implicit or explicit).
- Lack of awareness of avenues of support, such as university communications offices.
- Lack of confidence in representing their organisation or initiative appropriately or preventing reputational harm.
- Not knowing how to develop a user base.
- Not having enough "people power".
- Fear of backlash (for example, on social media).
- Lack of expertise or skills (such as graphic design or user research skills).
- Time constraints for the open science initiative's team and/or community.
- Others in the initiative not seeing the value of outreach work.
- Assuming the community's needs and preferences (for example, regarding social media platforms).
- Lack of resources or training which develops outreach, communications, marketing, and change management skills.
- The view that outreach is only for "finished products".

Table 1. Potential barriers to engaging in outreach activities for open science initiatives.

A total of 11 people responded to the survey in the 24 hours it was available. One person reported having less than one year of experience in Open Science; six reported having 1–5 years of experience; and four reported having more than five years of experience.

All respondents engaged in outreach for Open Science initiatives, with the most common activities being creating social media posts (8 respondents), community building activities (8 respondents), hosting conference talks or sessions (7 respondents),

managing email lists or newsletter (6 respondents), academic writing (6 respondents), and collecting feedback (5 respondents).

Respondents reported how comfortable they feel taking part in outreach activities for open science initiatives on a five-point Likert scale (1 = Not at all comfortable, 5 = Very comfortable). Overall, respondents reported feeling relatively comfortable conducting outreach activities for Open Science initiatives ($M = 4.0$, $SD = 1.1$). This likely reflects the sample's extensive experience in Open Science and the wide range of outreach activities they engage in. Whether this would generalise to the wider research community remains unclear, as do differences between academic disciplines and career stages.

The frequency of reported barriers to engaging in outreach activities for Open Science initiatives are reported in Table 2. The most frequently reported barriers were a lack of time and resources to conduct outreach activities, a lack of time within the community to engage with outreach, a sense of competing against other initiatives, lacking relevant skills, and struggling to "break through the noise".

These preliminary findings suggest that engagement in outreach activities for open science can be supported in the following ways:

1. Provision of time in work plans and event schedules for Open Science initiatives' teams to conduct outreach activities, and for community members of Open Science initiatives to engage in outreach activities.
2. Designation of funds for Open Science initiatives' outreach activities by funders and institutions.
3. The development of training in outreach, promotion, communications, and change management for Open Science leaders.

Theme	Barrier	Frequency
Knowledge and skills	I don't know how to create useful or effective outreach resources	1
	I lack the necessary skills, such as graphic design	5
	I'm not confident that I can represent the initiative correctly	2
	I'm not sure which channels to use (for example, which social media platforms to post on)	1
Prioritisation and resources	I don't have enough time to do outreach activities	7
	My community don't have enough time to engage in my outreach	5
	I do not have enough resources for outreach activities	6
	Outreach activities are not prioritised within my initiative	1
	My initiative doesn't feel like a finished product that can be shared	3
Community and environment	It feels like we're competing with other initiatives	5
	I'm not sure who to ask for help	0
	Lack of interest from the community	3
	There is too much content and I can't break through the noise	5

Table 2. Frequency of reported barriers to engaging in outreach activities for open science initiatives.

Reflection: Experience of Offering Outreach Services

During the Open Science Retreat 2025, we focused on outreach by creating social media posts to highlight participants' work. We began by asking individuals if they would be willing to post about their topic groups, take photos, and tag them on various social media platforms. To our surprise, everyone was very open to the idea and agreed to participate. We then asked participants about their topics so we could write summaries about their work. After that, we started crafting the posts and tagging them on the Digital Research Academy's official LinkedIn, BlueSky, and Mastodon accounts.

Our key takeaways are as follows:

- People were open to take part.
- Using the official Digital Research Academy accounts achieved good levels of reach.
- Tagging people in posts led to increased engagement.
- Scheduling posts is very important to avoid conflicting posts or overwhelming followers with too much content, especially in relation to events such as the Open Science Retreat.
- Using different social media platforms reaches different audiences.

Figure 2. Example social media post [on LinkedIn](#).

Resources

Resource	Brief description
<p>Atkinson, Malcolm, David De Roure, Jano van Hemert, and Danius Michaelides. 'Shaping Ramps for Data-Intensive Research'. Conference presented at the UK e-Science All Hands Meeting 2010, June 2010. http://eprints.soton.ac.uk/id/eprint/271235</p>	<p>Intellectual ramps supporting the gradual introduction of innovations.</p>
<p>Bautista, C., Alfuraiji, N., Drangowska-Way, A., Gangwani, K., De Flamingh, A., & Bourne, P. E. (2022). Ten simple rules for improving communication among scientists. <i>PLOS Computational Biology</i>, 18(6), e1010130. https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1010130</p>	<p>A concise guide of communication possibilities and skill improvement strategies for different stages of scientific career</p>
<p>Baxter, K., Courage, C., & Caine, K. (2015). <i>Understanding your users: a practical guide to user research methods</i>. Morgan Kaufmann.</p>	<p>A practical guide to user research methods.</p>
<p>Bik, H. M., Dove, A. D. M., Goldstein, M. C., Helm, R. R., MacPherson, R., Martini, K., Warneke, A., & McClain, C. (2015). Ten Simple Rules for Effective Online Outreach. <i>PLOS Computational Biology</i>, 11(4), e1003906. https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1003906</p>	<p>A guide for effective online outreach from the authors of a highly visited marine science blog.</p>
<p>Chunpir, H. I., Ludwig, T., & Williams, D. N. (2015). Evolution of e-Research: from infrastructure development to service orientation. In <i>Design, User Experience, and Usability: Interactive Experience Design: 4th International Conference, DUXU 2015, Held as Part of HCI International 2015, Los Angeles, CA, USA, August 2-7, 2015, Proceedings, Part III 4</i> (pp. 25-35). Springer International Publishing.</p>	<p>Methodology for user research.</p>
<p>Community Engagement 101: Ultimate Beginner's Guide https://visiblenetworklabs.com/guides/community-engagement-101/</p>	<p>Tools and actionable plans at every stage of the community engagement.</p>
<p>Dawson, D. (DeDe). (2018). Effective Practices and Strategies for Open Access Outreach: A Qualitative Study. <i>Journal of Librarianship and Scholarly Communication</i>, 6(1), Article 1. https://doi.org/10.7710/2162-3309.2216</p>	<p>Results of a survey about the effective strategies of libraries' outreach related to Open Access.</p>

<p>Dearing, James W., and Jeffrey G. Cox. 'Diffusion Of Innovations Theory, Principles, And Practice'. <i>Health Affairs</i> 37, no. 2 (1 February 2018): 183–90. https://doi.org/10.1377/hlthaff.2017.1104</p>	<p>Highlights the importance of early adopters and early majority within a community to bring about change.</p>
<p>Driscoll, A., & Lynton, E. A. (2023). <i>Making outreach visible: A guide to documenting professional service and outreach</i>. Routledge, Taylor & Francis Group.</p>	<p>A guide to documenting and making your services visible with examples for different academic fields.</p>
<p>https://digitaltonto.com/2024/heres-why-creating-awareness-is-usually-a-waste-of-time/</p>	<p>Blog post calling for more evidence-based approaches for change.</p>
<p>Outreach Training Program (OTP) https://www.acs.org/education/outreach/outreach-training-program.html</p>	<p>A free on-demand online course. It is stated that ACS membership is not required.</p>
<p>Resources on Community Engagement & Outreach https://www.aaas.org/programs/on-call-scientists/resources-community-engagement-outreach</p>	<p>Links to many additional resources on community engagement and outreach.</p>
<p>Restel K, Depping, R. Bericht zum 1. NFDI4Health User Survey. Publisso, 2023. https://doi.org/10.4126/FRL01-006461780</p>	<p>Relevant user survey in this space.</p>
<p>Robson, S. G., Baum, M. A., Beaudry, J. L., Beitner, J., Brohmer, H., Chin, J. M., Jasko, K., Kouros, C. D., Laukkonen, R. E., Moreau, D., Searston, R. A., Slagter, H. A., Steffens, N. K., Tangen, J. M., & Thomas, A. (2021). Promoting Open Science: A Holistic Approach to Changing Behaviour. <i>Collabra: Psychology</i>, 7(1). https://doi.org/10.1525/collabra.30137</p>	<p>Actions that researchers can take to promote Open Science among peers (inspired by principles of behaviour change: make it easy, social, and attractive).</p>
<p>Schmidt C, Hanne J, Moore J et al. Research data management for bioimaging: the 2021 NFDI4BIOIMAGE community survey [version 2; peer review: 2 approved]. <i>F1000Research</i> 2022, 11:638 (https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.121714.2)</p>	<p>Relevant user survey in this space.</p>
<p>The Genetics Society of America. Science Communication Resources. https://genetics-gsa.org/science-communication-resources/</p>	<p>Links to resources on community engagement and outreach (podcasts, social media, training opportunities etc).</p>
<p>Science Europe https://scienceeurope.org/our-priorities/open-science/science-europe-members-practices-on-open-science/</p>	<p>Provides a list of resources about Open Science in your country.</p>

Swan, A. & UNESCO (Eds.). (2012). Policy guidelines for the development and promotion of open access. United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization.	Outlines strategies to promote Open Access at the policy level.
Task Force User Research of NFDI survey on user research within the NFDI, questionnaire: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15224572	The Taskforce User Research aims to promote the exchange of experience on the topic of user research.
The Message Box https://www.compassscicomm.org/leadership-development/the-message-box/#get-started The version tailored to scientists: https://www.compassscicomm.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/05/The-Message-Box-Workbook.pdf	A tool helping formulate your message and tailor the communication to your audience.
Why Design is Hard by Scott Berkun, https://scottberkun.com/why-design-is-hard/ ; ISBN 0983873194	This book teaches designers and experts how to overcome the people, power, and systems that currently hold them back.
Woitowich, N. C., Hunt, G. C., Muhammad, L. N., & Garbarino, J. (2022). Assessing motivations and barriers to science outreach within academic science research settings: A mixed-methods survey. <i>Frontiers in Communication</i> , 7, 907762. https://doi.org/10.3389/fcomm.2022.907762	Survey about activities, motivations, barriers, and attitudes towards science outreach.

Table 3. Resources about engaging in outreach activities for open science initiatives.

Appendix: "Outreach for Open Science Initiatives"

Survey

Introduction

We would like to learn more about outreach activities among open science initiatives, services, and infrastructures ("open science initiatives" from now on). This survey will ask you about the outreach activities you engage in for your open science initiatives; the barriers you face to engaging in outreach; and what about an open science initiative gets your attention.

We are defining outreach activities as **anything which reaches out to and/or engages the community around your open science initiative**. This can include making social media posts, sending newsletters, community building activities, conference sessions, creating podcasts, writing content which is aimed at sharing your initiative (such as blogging or journal articles), vlogging, and collecting feedback from the community.

This study is being conducted in line with the British Psychological Society (2021) Code of Human Research Ethics, although it does not have Research Ethics Committee / Institutional Review Board approval. All responses are anonymous. If you have questions or concerns, please contact Bethan Iley: bethan@we-are-ols.org

We anticipate that this will take most people ~5 minutes to complete.

Tell us about your outreach activities.

What outreach activities are you currently engaged in for the open science initiative(s) you are part of?

- Creating social media posts
- Managing email lists or sending newsletters
- Blogging
- Academic writing, such as preprints or journal articles
- Hosting conference talks or sessions
- Collecting feedback, such as user research

- Creating podcasts
- Creating video content, such as vlogs or TikToks
- Community building activities
- Other: _____

Imagine you were asked to conduct outreach activities for the open science initiative(s) you are part of. How comfortable would you feel doing this?

1. Not at all comfortable
- 2.
- 3.
- 4.
5. Very comfortable

Tell us about the barriers which prevent you engaging in outreach activities for your open science initiative(s).

If you do not experience any barriers, please leave this section blank.

What barriers do you face to engaging in outreach activities for your open science initiative(s)?

Knowledge and skills

- I don't know how to create useful or effective outreach resources
- I lack the necessary skills, such as graphic design
- I'm not confident that I can represent the initiative correctly
- I'm not sure which channels to use (for example, which social media platforms to post on)
- Other: _____

Prioritisation and resources

- I don't have enough time to do outreach activities
- My community don't have enough time to engage in my outreach
- I do not have enough resources for outreach activities
- Outreach activities are not prioritised within my initiative

- My initiative doesn't feel like a finished product that can be shared
- Other: _____

Community and environment

- It feels like we're competing with other initiatives
- I'm not sure who to ask for help
- Lack of interest from the community
- There is too much content and I can't break through the noise
- Other: _____

Something else: _____

Tell us what gets you excited about other open science initiatives.

If you're not sure, please leave the question blank.

When you're scrolling through social media, what gets your attention regarding open science initiatives?

What makes you remember an open science initiative when you're attending a conference or event (within or outside of your organisation)?

What makes you want to read a journal article or book about an open science initiative?

What makes you feel connected to an open science initiative?

To finish up...

How long have you been involved in open science?

- Less than 1 year
- 1-5 years
- More than 5 years

What resources have you seen (online or offline) about promoting open science initiatives?

What are some memorable examples of outreach you've seen from open science initiatives?

Do you have any other feedback or comments?

For example, things which weren't clear or suggestions for questions we should include in the survey.
